

DEVELOPMENT OF LISTENING SKILLS IN YOUNG LEARNERS.**Akgayeva Khumay***Student of Berdak Stat University*xumayakgayeva3@gmail.com

Abstract. This article examines the importance of developing listening skills in young learners while learning English as a foreign language. Listening is considered a core language skill that directly influences the development of speaking, reading, and writing abilities. The study highlights listening as an active and cognitive process involving attention, perception, memory, and comprehension. The article also analyzes the views of prominent linguists and educators such as Stephen Krashen, Gary Buck, and H. Douglas Brown on listening comprehension. In addition, practical methods for improving listening skills among young learners are discussed, including the use of podcasts, songs, movies, audio stories, and interactive listening games. The findings emphasize the crucial role of teachers in creating appropriate learning conditions and applying effective strategies to enhance attentive listening skills in children.

Keywords: listening skills; young learners; listening comprehension; English language teaching; language skills; attention and memory; interactive listening; audio-visual materials; teaching methods.

Learning English is very important in today's developing era. One of the important aspects in learning this foreign language is the skill of listening comprehension. The reason is that a student who can freely understand and hear words will certainly not have difficulty in developing the remaining skills. The reason for this is that the remaining 3 skills (speaking, writing, reading) are closely related to listening. It would not be an exaggeration to say that greater success will be achieved if this activity begins with young people, that is, schoolchildren. Here is what Dalai Lama said: "When you talk, you are only repeating what you already know. But if you listen, you may learn something new"

Listening is one of the methods by which humans attempt to make sense of the surrounding world. By allowing us to hear and interpret environmental sounds, listening serves as an aural vehicle for comprehension development. Listening is language skill that actually begins prior to birth and continues to be an essential, interactive process throughout life. Typically, listening receives much less emphasis in the classroom than do other language arts.[1] Listening is the most important of the 4 skills not only in learning English, but also in mastering any other language. Because listening skills are not limited to just listening, but help to understand the speech more deeply, analyze it, understand its meaning, and find the right answer as a result. Attention and memory play an important role in this process. Students make many mistakes if they are not attentive to the speech they are listening to or if they do not remember the speech they are listening to, that is, if they do not know what topic is being discussed. The skill of listening teaches students to listen and focus their attention. When a student is attentive to what they are listening to, their ability to analyze it and remember it later is higher.

Some people consider listening a passive skill. In essence, the ability to listen requires the active participation of the listener. The listener rebuilds the speech they hear in their mind and adapts it to themselves. This process requires more activity than we think. Also, listening requires not only activity, but also a response. By learning this skill, children can learn English faster than before.[2] Listening also plays an important role in speaking. Both of these constitute oral speech. As listening develops, speaking also develops. Through these 2 skills, the student receives information. If a student cannot pronounce words correctly, they will not recognize them when listening and will not understand their meaning.

Scientists of the world have expressed the following opinions about listening comprehension in their works.

1. American linguist Stephen Krashen, founder of the "Comprehensible Input Hypothesis," says: "When learning a new language, we do not create a language system ourselves, but we naturally assimilate it by listening to the information that is understood." Krashen considers listening to be the center, the beginning of the natural learning process. According to it, a child also learns their native language by listening first, and then begins to speak.

2. Gary Buck analyzes listening comprehension based on a psycholinguistic model in his work "Assessing Listening." Buck says: "In listening, the human brain performs many mental operations simultaneously - it recognizes the sound, connects it to the word, and turns it into meaning." Thus, listening is an active, complex mental activity in which perception, attention, memory, and language knowledge work together.

3. American pedagogue H. Douglas Brown says in his work "Teaching by Principles": "Listening is the most frequently used language skill in everyday communication." He believes that in real life, people spend 40-50% of their communication time listening, 30% talking, and the rest reading and writing. Therefore, when teaching listening, it is important to use real materials (interviews, podcasts, conversations, films). Brown calls listening an interactive process because it involves the interaction between the listener and the speaker.

The student may encounter many difficulties during listening. Unfamiliarity of grammatical structure, emotions and shortcomings in the process of hearing directly from the speaker, ambiguity of words or lack of attention, etc. Let's consider several methods for developing listening skills.

1. Listen to a podcast. Listening to 1 podcast every day is more effective than we think in improving listening skills. Mainly speeches by great personalities and job interviews. The podcast also greatly helps us pronounce words correctly and without mistakes (for beginners, of course, with subtitles).

2. Watch more English songs and movies. This is an effective method for young learners. An excellent material for use during the lesson. Attention can be focused through English cartoons or short films. It is necessary not only to observe, but also to analyze what events took place, the negative and positive sides of the characters.

3. Listening to story-rich, mysterious audio stories. Not limiting themselves to just listening, the teacher should engage in more interaction with students, asking them what they have learned, understood, and summarized during the lesson. This method is useful for listening, memory enhancement, and speaking.

4. Playing listening games in the classroom. Working on listening quizzes using small stage performances or various electronic platforms. Through this, students listen to the text or conversation and choose the correct answers.

The main thing is how to apply these methods is in the teacher's hands. First of all, it is necessary to create suitable conditions in the classroom. The

information provided to young people should correspond to their level. Most importantly, the teacher should develop methods for developing attentive listening skills in the child.

Listening is the ability of students to understand, comprehend, and respond to the teacher's or other people's thoughts. Why do most young learners have lower listening skills compared to others? The only reason for this is that it doesn't spend much time listening. For listening to be effective, the learner needs to work on themselves for hours. Listening strengthens children's reading, writing, speaking skills and prepares them for independent reading and learning in the future. High-ranking companies also prioritize developing listening skills in their employees. Because if the listener does not listen attentively to the speaker's speech, there may be a break when reaching the main point, that is, the listener will not be able to receive the rest of the information and will have difficulty answering. And this works to your detriment anywhere, whether at work or during lessons. John Marshall says: "Listening well is just as powerful a means of influence as speaking well."

Most listeners listen not to understand the material, but to respond. Because they know their answers will follow one after another, they sit and wait. However, it's common to find it difficult to find answers when encountering distracting lectures. To avoid such difficulties, it is important for the learner to perceive the material they are listening to, understand its content, and memorize it. Considering the above, it can be concluded that listening is the core of language learning. Effective listening allows students to clearly and fully understand the speech, be active during the conversation, and give a corresponding and accurate answer to the speaker's opinion. It should also be noted that the teacher's role plays an important role in the development of this skill. Effective listening skills should be enriched through the use of various games, questions and answers, and active methods in the learning process.

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